

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF STRATEGIC MANAGERIAL EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION: EVIDENCE FROM THE HCSO IN HUNGARY AND INDIS IN SRI LANKAN MIS SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Nowadays, Management Information Systems (MIS) are playing an important role in public administration and are expected to actively contribute to strategic digital governance through evidence-based decision-making. This study examines the management efficiency of the MIS of the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (HCSO) in Hungary and the Integrated National Data and Information System (INDIS) in Sri Lanka. Based on secondary data and using published report information, both these contexts have been studied. A structural analysis has been conducted based on SWOT assessments and five management strategies. The study of management strategies such as time efficiency, cost control, fitness for purpose, stakeholder trust, and adaptability also revealed the advanced technological integration and instabilities in HCSO's MIS. At the same time, the strengths and developmental challenges of the INDIS's transparency were identified. This study demonstrates how emerging systems like INDIS can benefit from mature models such as HCSO and examines the current effectiveness of INDIS.

1. Introduction

An examination of the past few decades shows that public administration has achieved significant developments through the use of Management Information Systems (MIS). These systems help manage structural governments, implement policies, and promote citizen participation and accountability (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2015; Rosenbloom et al., 2015). Therefore, numerical methods and MIS tools have become essential for decision-making, performance monitoring, and transparency today (United Nations, 1994; Eurostat, 2018). In Sri Lanka, the Information and Communication Technology Agency (ICTA) and e-Sri Lanka explain the role of ICT in modernizing public administration. Although the Integrated National Data Information System (INDIS), which has been operational since 2011, has been in operation, a research gap has emerged due to the lack of studies examining its progress. This study aims to fill this gap.

The main objective of the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (HCSO) is to make improvements through the knowledge of well-organized public administration strategies based on MIS principles. Integrated numerical systems and digital structures within the HCSO (MIS) have enhanced sound decision-making, efficiency, and accountability (Kárpáti, 2008). Furthermore, despite the large literature on HCSO, there is a dearth of studies comparing MIS-based administration between a European Union country and a South Asian country in transition. This study aims to evaluate management efficiency, compare structural management outcomes between two culturally, socio-economically, and administratively different government systems, and provide an understanding of the interplay between mature and digital government systems. The management performance and public service efficiency of MIS frameworks are measured by analysing factors such as time efficiency, cost control, operational suitability, stakeholder trust, and adaptability to

change. This research aims to provide Sri Lankan policymakers and administrators with practical lessons from Hungary's experience and identify strategies to improve management efficiency.

Public administration is the process of implementing policies, managing programs, and promoting public trust by balancing legal responsibilities with managerial efficiency. Ensuring efficient service delivery in areas such as health, education, and supporting infrastructure (Rosenbloom, Kravchuk, & Clerkin, 2015). Strong public administration creates a foundation for transparency and institutional strength, and enhances public value (United Nations, 1994). Public administration systems vary globally. The Asian model combines centralized planning with social participation (United Nations, 1994). The African system is decentralized, with a focus on local accountability (Karyeija, 2012). The quality and transparency of the production frameworks are highly valued, and it is important that they comply with international standards (European Statistical Practice Code) (Eurostat, 2017). The Japanese system, supported by institutions such as the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), USAID, and FCDO, promotes public awareness through international cooperation and institutional development (JICA, n.d.).

The Hungarian Central Statistical Office (HCSO) has developed a data-driven Management Information System (MIS) that will be used to modernize public administration. The data entry system (decentralized data entry) introduced by HCSO in 1980 initiated the development of information systems during the period 1984-1988 (United Nations Digital Library, 1982, 1984). In 2005, the theoretical foundations and the complete system concept were developed, and the project was officially submitted in April 2006 (Hungarian Central Statistical Office [HCSO], 2006). According to Kárpáti (2008), the MIS system is designed according to international best practices and decision-support mechanisms. Furthermore, guidelines such as the balanced scorecard have been shown in the years since the HCSO, the national digital transformation program. To expand the MIS system structure, data transparency, and source management, focus has been placed on data digitization projects such as "150 Years of Hungarian Statistics" (Cseh, 2020; Daily News Hungary, 2023). Today, the MIS system of this HCSO has evolved into an administrative tool that enables fair, efficient, and positive decision-making (Cseh, 2020).

In parallel, the Integrated National Data and Information System (INDIS project) in Sri Lanka was launched with the aim of digital administration and positive decision-making for public administration. This project was implemented under the UNDP and other international participation of ICTA, and aims for transparency from on-site data collection to reporting (UNDP Sri Lanka, 2022). Over the past few years, the scope of the project has expanded, and monitoring methods, dashboards, and MIS frameworks have been introduced. Currently, there is a great deal of progress in INDIS, and the sensitive data can be seen working in conjunction with all state ministries and agencies (UNDP Sri Lanka, 2022). While these advances have not been undone, challenges remain due to limited skills among government officials. The Department of Census and Statistics (DCS) takes the lead role in this process. Also, publication data such as the Statistical Pocket Book, which provides key insights into population, agriculture, industry, and national accounts, is provided (DCS, 2024). The Central Bank of Sri Lanka (CBSL) has also made a key contribution in providing the economic and social data required for planning (CBSL, n.d.).

2. Research Methodology

The main research question of this study was "How does the management efficiency of INDIS, Sri Lanka, using MIS systems improve, and what are the factors associated with these improvements?" In addition, several sub-research questions were based on research, and data collection and analysis were conducted. "What lessons can be learned from the developments of INDIS (Sri Lanka)?, which uses MIS methods, and HCSO (MIS), Hungary?", "How does the management efficiency of HCSO and INDIS affect time efficiency, cost control, objectives, and building stakeholder trust?", "What

kind of contribution do the strengths, weaknesses, threats, and risks (SWOT) of HCSO and INDIS MIS systems make to the management structure?".

This research was conducted using a qualitative and comparative research design, with data analysis based entirely on secondary data analysis. Without using primary research to collect new data, a study of existing published reports, policy documents, scientific articles, and official scientific reports related to both contexts has been conducted. Published reports from the Hungarian Central Statistical Office (HCSO) and the Integrated National Data Information System (INDIS) of Sri Lanka were used as the main data sources for this study.

In this study, data collection and analysis were conducted on Managerial Effectiveness in both contexts based on key operational indicators such as Time efficiency, Cost control, Fit for purpose, Stakeholder trust, and Adaptability for changes. These indicators were revealed by Walker in his study in 2013. Furthermore, comparisons were made between the two environments using these indicators. To achieve this management efficiency, an analysis of the existing internal and external situation of HCSO and INDIS was conducted. It is based on (SWOT) analysis, which categorizes strengths and weaknesses as internal characteristics, and threats and opportunities as external characteristics, and conducts data collection and analysis.

Using this method, it became possible to openly analyse the differences and similarities between a mature program MIS environment and a development environment that was a southern start-up system. This enabled cross-learning to provide practical recommendations for the development of public administration. Not only that, but what lessons can be learned from Hungary, a member of the European Union, in a transition economy like Sri Lanka, in developing digital governance and efficient administration? This is done to suggest, if possible, that lessons can be learned from the developing Sri Lankan context and the Hungarian context.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (*Walker, 2013*) (*Andrews et al., 2011*) (*own edition*)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. SWOT Analysis of HCSO MIS

In this study, HCSO identified several strengths of MIS. The main strength of this system is the ability to perform accurate and fast reporting using an integrated database and OLAP dashboards. This helps to minimize errors and support fair decision-making. Transparency fosters public trust (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021). This system has maintained its trust because it operates in a stable institutional environment. Due to constant use, it has the ability to report sensitive government data. Key among its strengths is its broad coverage of operational areas, due to the inclusion of business intelligence. EU standards are linked to international compliance and interoperability (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021).

At the same time, this identification also has weaknesses. Due to the technical complexity, it is costly to update due to the need for specialist training and continuous professional development (Kárpáti, 2008). There are many risks associated with IT disruptions, which have a direct impact on reporting delays. When data quality is compromised, it can lead to high maintenance costs, as well as incomplete documentation. The strong opposition to the EU context leads to weaknesses such as user and fragmented processes (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021). This project also identifies several important opportunities. HCSO MIS can benefit from integration with EU digital governance programs by adopting advanced technologies to enhance interoperability (European Commission, 2021).

There are also a number of important opportunities identified through this project. The HCSO MIS system will be integrated and implemented with EU digital governance programs. Accordingly, the use of high-tech innovations has the potential to improve interoperability and reap benefits (European Commission, 2021). Because predictive modeling exists, there is also the ability to anticipate future developments and disruptions. Many external opportunities, such as big data analytics, cloud computing, user training programs, etc., have contributed to its development. There are more opportunities for ISO certifications and transparent data gateways, as social collaboration with national statistical offices exists. These opportunities have improved the efficiency, structural value, and decision-making capacity of the system (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021).

The HCSO project has identified numerous threats to data usage. The system poses numerous cybersecurity risks that could compromise the integrity of data and the trust of stakeholders (European Commission, 2021). Political or regulatory changes within the country may necessitate frequent, costly changes (Kárpáti, 2018; European Commission, 2021). Therefore, not only budgetary constraints, but also stakeholder resistance to these changes is a constant threat. Privacy and legal obligations created by integrating multi-source data create risks (Kárpáti, 2018; European Commission, 2021).

3.2.SWOT Analysis of INDIS Project

The INDIS project also has many of the identified strengths. The main value of the INDIS system in Sri Lanka is that it integrates several ministries and provides centralized data collection. Therefore, financial, administrative, and operational data are also centralized. This INDIS system provides a unified and fair view of government activities, facilitating decision-making (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021). This system highly values transparency. Public trust has increased as administrative equity, financial monitoring, and reporting are at a high level. Designing procedures and sharing data between government agencies promotes a culture of accountability (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021).

However, several weaknesses have also been identified. Although the INDIS project has been created by integrating several different ministries, limited collaboration can be established between the sectors. This creates problems in reporting sensitive data. Lack of ICT skills and technical capabilities leads to low contribution to updates. It faces challenges such as resource constraints and unstable procedures. Political instability and participation lead to system inefficiency and reduce the reliability of the data produced (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021).

However, several important opportunities were also identified in the INDIS project. Since the system is very flexible, it has the potential to learn lessons from mature MIS frameworks. There is potential to leverage ongoing international support from organizations such as the WHO, World Bank, and ICTA for advanced analytics, cloud computing, and big data integration. There is potential to improve staff training and establish collaboration with inter-ministerial and international organizations. The government also facilitates the implementation of standard rules for reliability and transparency (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021).

The INDIS project also faces many external threats. Political instability, frequent changes of government, and institutional divisions reduce efficiency. Bureaucratic resistance and technical differences between offices reduce the accuracy of data. Cybersecurity risks are constant and pose a major threat to data privacy. By combining data from multiple sources, legal responsibilities can also be compromised (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021). These risks can undermine system performance and public trust if not properly managed.

3.3. Managerial Effectiveness of HCSO MIS

HCSO's Management Information System (MIS) improves **time efficiency** through the use of automated reporting tools. This capability minimizes data delays and provides accurate and timely data. This allows data to be quickly and easily transferred to decision-makers, which in turn enables faster policymaking (Kárpáti, 2008; Cseh, 2020; European Commission, 2021). However, complex automated processes also run the risk of slowing down the workflow. The MIS system strengthens **cost control** by providing detailed reports to relevant parties. Regardless of which political group is elected, these systems facilitate efficient allocation of resources and budget control, thereby reducing additional costs and increasing operational efficiency (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021). However, operational costs can increase due to the high need for professional training and technical expertise. However, reporting systems and digital tools can eliminate additional tasks and increase efficiency, Buics & Süle revealed in 2020.

HCSO's MIS system is designed to align with organizational objectives, **fit for the purposes** and operational goals, thereby supporting sound decision-making and policy planning. It ensures the production of high-quality statistical reports, as they can comply with EU and institutional standards and objectives (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021). However, the limited ability to respond to new directives or sudden policy changes will minimize the system's adaptability (Cseh, 2022). Building **stakeholder trust** is another important aspect of an MIS system. This trust is built through transparent data reporting and compliance with international standards. Providing accurate information in policymaking strengthens trust. However, user resistance to new systems and political interference have undermined trust and usage (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021; Cseh, 2020).

Finally, the HCSO examines whether the MIS system is designed **to adapt to a rapidly changing** environment. This includes new reporting requirements, legal changes, and efforts to keep up with advanced technology tools such as AI and predictive analytics. However, institutional changes and new policies have limited capabilities, indicating the need for further updating of the system (Kárpáti, 2008; European Commission, 2021).

3.4. Managerial Effectiveness of Sri Lanka's INDIS Project

INDIS is designed to provide live and **real-time monitoring** of financial and operational activities, reducing bureaucratic delays and allowing officials and policymakers to make faster decisions (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021). As automated workflows are in place, additional tasks are reduced. Problems arise due to collaboration issues between departments, and low ICT skills that do not achieve the desired efficiencies. This system improves **cost control** through centralized data collection and reporting, reduces administrative workload, improves resource allocation, and increases financial efficiency (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021). However, high initial investment, staff training, and maintenance requirements can lead to increased operating costs. The INDIS project is designed to meet operational and structural requirements to **fit with the institutional purposes**. It can operate with a modular architecture that can be customized to meet institution-specific needs. This supports the objectives of information collection and analysis (ICTA, 2020). However, constraints in customization and misalignment with workflows can limit efficiency and pose a risk of achieving desired objectives (Ministry of Finance, 2021).

This system, INDIS, promotes transparency, accountability, and trust. Open data reporting builds trust among stakeholders and citizens. It also increases **trust** between policymakers and institutions. However, maintenance delays and data exchange issues between departments can reduce confidence in the system (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021). The key feature that is essential when examining how the INDIS system copes with **adaptability for changes** is its flexibility. Flexible infrastructure, predictive analytics, and AI integration offer the potential to adapt to changing and emerging administrative needs. As political interference increases, flexibility can be challenged by budgetary constraints, lack of technical expertise, and bureaucratic resistance (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021).

3.5. Qualitative Aspects in which HCSO MIS Excels Compared to INDIS

Several features are being implemented in Hungary's HCSO MIS, but they have not yet been implemented in the INDIS project. HCSO operates in accordance with European standards that ensure reliability, data governance, international compliance, and easily achieves the desired goals. It was revealed that HCSO MIS has higher quality compared to INDIS due to the use of visualization and intelligence. Although HCSO has improved efficiency by performing complex data analytics such as MIS, OLAP dashboards and predictive modeling, INDIS is still in the development stage and has not yet acquired such technical capabilities.

The institutional stability of the HCSO MIS is high, with continuous updates and robust cybersecurity and risk management in line with European Union regulatory guidelines. However, due to limited resources and technical shortcomings, INDIS still faces challenges in these tasks. As a result, it is still not possible to protect sensitive information 100%. Ultimately, it was revealed that INDIS is capable of providing comprehensive administrative integration. However, when compared to HCSO MIS, HCSO MIS excels in terms of accuracy, reliability, security, and adherence to global best practices. Therefore, in a developing state environment, the lessons that can be learned from HCSO MIS are very relevant to the context in which Sri Lanka is still developing.

Aspect	HCSO MIS – Unique Strengths	Why INDIS Lacks This
International Standard	Data governance and operations are conducted under international standards such as the EU, ensuring reliability.	Operates only at the national level
Advanced Data Analytics & BI Tools	Visualize, analyse, and predict complex data using BI tools such as advanced data analytics and OLAP dashboards.	Lacks international forecasting model capacity.
Institutional Stability & Continuity	Mature operations and consistent updates, maintaining institutional stability and continuity within the EU framework	Disaster systems frequently face political and administrative changes that affect their continuity.
Data Quality & Accuracy	Data quality and standardization ensure accuracy	Struggles with data inconsistencies and discrepancies
Cybersecurity & Risk Management	EU-regulated, uses cybersecurity strategies and risk management frameworks, ensuring data protection	Resource constraints, skill gaps, and lack of advanced cybersecurity measures
Long-Term Technical Maturity	Represents an advanced MIS that is mature and refined through technological development due to long-term use	INDIS is in early development, so there are limited and slow updates

Table 01: Qualitative Aspects in which HCSO MIS Excels Compared to INDIS

3.6. Qualitative Aspects in which INDIS Excels Compared to HCSO MIS

The INDIS project, characterized by broad government integration and transparency, is a turning point in a developing country. The INDIS project, which centralizes financial, administrative, and operational data across multiple ministries, facilitates improved coordination, real-time monitoring, and evidence-based policymaking (ICTA, 2020; Ministry of Finance, 2021). It is consistently committed to promoting public participation, building accountability, and citizen trust. In contrast, the EU-compliant and sector-specific HCSO MIS appears to have a more limited scope, as it has fewer opportunities for flexibility. INDIS not only supports continuous data reporting but also strategic decision-making. It improves cost efficiency as there is less duplication. This will serve as a driver for digital governance and public sector innovation in a developing country.

The HCSO MIS is considered excellent because it demonstrates technological sophistication, statistical accuracy, and compliance with EU standards. However, HCSO is seen as less flexible than INDIS in terms of financial oversight, integration across ministries, higher adaptability, and direct public accountability. For the further development of HCSO MIS, INDIS can also draw valuable lessons.

Area	INDIS Project (Sri Lanka) Unique Strengths	Why HCSO MIS Lacks This
Cross-Ministerial Integration	Financial, administrative and operational data are well centralized across multiple ministries.	There is no integration across the government, and the focus is mainly on statistics.
Administrative Transparency	Promotes open governance and transparency through participation in government institutions	There is a lack of transparency across the government, and some data accuracy is targeted.
Fiscal Management Focus	Focuses on real-time financial monitoring and resource utilization	Finance or management is not handled and the focus is mainly on statistics and reporting..
Modular Customization	Uses a modular architecture that allows for customization, considering the usage of each organization	Limited flexibility can be seen, adhering to a standardized EU framework.
Broader Governance Scope	Supports the implementation of strategic decisions across the government, not just within one sector	Since it mainly serves the National Statistical Office, it does not involve multiple ministries or institutions.
Adaptability to Developing Contexts	There is a greater chance of establishing a high level of flexibility in the international context.	A mature and complex system exists, with little flexibility for new innovations.
Public Accountability Orientation	There is transparent data access that strengthens the trust of citizens and policymakers.	In ensuring internal statistical accuracy, and does not focus on public transparency or civic participation.
Cost Efficiency through Centralization	Efficiency is increased by integrating multiple systems into one, reducing duplication.	The use of specialized subsystems can increase operational costs

Table 02: Qualitative Aspects in which INDIS Excels Compared to HCSO MIS

4. Comparative Conclusion

Mature MIS frameworks such as HCSO benefit from stability, technological advancements, and established processes. Emerging systems such as INDIS have significant potential but are found to face organizational and infrastructural barriers. There are many lessons that Sri Lanka's INDIS can learn from the experiences of looking at the strengths and weaknesses of HCSO, and the benefits that INDIS brings to the country as a result of its great development are also many. Therefore, according

to the research problem, it is confirmed that the INDIS project has achieved high management efficiency to date. It also revealed the need for advanced contexts to foster data-driven governance, strengthen public trust, and address technological complexities. Overall, both scenarios aim to achieve sustainable public sector transformation towards effective MIS implementation. There are many lessons to be learned from each of these scenarios.

5. Recommendations

5.1. Recommendations for HCSO MIS (Hungary)

- **Improving adaptability in terms of system flexibility.**
It is best to introduce systematic changes in the MIS to allow for faster response considering EU policies or updates. This can enable targeted system improvements while maintaining operational continuity.
- **Considering user participation.**
Recommend to implementing change management, and conducting user training programs, can help reduce resistance in development processes and improve the efficiency of system acceptance.
- **Integrate AI and predictive analytics.**
It is recommended to further strengthen strategic decision-making by integrating artificial intelligence (AI) with existing predictive analytics, such as OLAP and BI tools.
- **Strengthening cybersecurity and risk management frameworks.**
It is appropriate to take measures to protect sensitive data against potential digital threats, by using and upgrading EU-aligned cybersecurity models, for example, zero-trust frameworks.
- **Increase transparency and promote public data accessibility.**
Through the use of open data dashboards, public reporting systems can be expanded. This research proposes a suitable method that is expected to improve data accountability and public trust.

5.2. Recommendations for INDIS (Sri Lanka)

- **Developing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) training and management.**
It is recommended that continuous professional development programs be established at the ministry level to enhance ICT literacy among government officials who handle data, as well as to strengthen immediate expertise.
- **Adopting international standards and interoperability frameworks.**
It is recommended that aligning INDIS with the Statistical Code of Practice by adopting recognized methodological standards such as ISO 8000, EU, etc. will help improve reliability.
- **Strengthening cybersecurity and data protection systems.**
It is recommended not only storing encrypted data, but also implementing security audits and structured approaches that help prevent data breaches and improve stakeholder trust.
- **Improve governance through inter-ministerial coordination.**
It is recommended to establish a collaborative, centralized MIS governance authority, developing coordination of data management across institutions.

6. Final Remarks

The analysis highlights that while mature MIS frameworks such as HCSO benefit from stability, technological advancements, and established processes due to their international presence, emerging systems such as INDIS face significant organizational and infrastructural barriers.

By learning from the strengths and experiences of HCSO, Sri Lanka can strategically improve the management efficiency of INDIS and strengthen public trust.

Similarly, considering the technical complexities, HCSO can continue to evolve and further develop trust by increasing the adaptability of the system.

Overall, lessons can be learned from the developed context to the developing context, and vice versa, from the context in which development takes place to the developed context. Policymakers should therefore focus on achieving sustainable public sector management transformations.

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